

Transition Metal Diene Complexes in Organic Synthesis. Part-17¹. Studies directed towards the Iron-mediated Synthesis of 2-Oxygenated Carbazole Alkaloids

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We describe some studies directed towards the synthesis of 2-oxygenated carbazole alkaloids by iron-mediated oxidative coupling of 1,3-cyclohexadiene and the corresponding 3-oxygenated arylamine derivative. The process involves a consecutive formation of a carbon-carbon bond via electrophilic aromatic substitution with an iron-complexed cyclohexadienylum cation and subsequent carbon-nitrogen bond formation via oxidative cyclisation. Using this methodology a synthesis of the biogenetically important alkaloid 2-methoxy-3-methylcarbazole is described.

Over the past decades a large number of carbazole alkaloids has been isolated from various natural sources². Considerable interest in these compounds derives from the fact that many derivatives represent pharmacologically active substances. Although several different methods for the construction of the carbazole skeleton were known³, the recent isolation of higher functionalised and especially selectively oxygenated carbazole alkaloids required the development of novel strategies for the synthesis of the carbazole framework⁴.

We devised an iron-mediated synthesis of the carbazole ring system which takes advantage of a consecutive iron-induced formation of a carbon-carbon and a carbon-nitrogen bond⁵. This two-step process involves electrophilic aromatic substitution of an arylamine by a tricarbonyliron-complexed cyclohexadienylum cation followed by oxidative cyclisation to the carbazole framework. The characteristic feature of our approach is, that completely functionalised arylamines can be used and therefore, highly convergent syntheses of the envisaged carbazole alkaloids are feasible.

A novel class of antibiotics isolated from streptomycetes by Japanese groups attracted our attention for the first application of the methodol-

ogy described above. Nakamura and Marumo reported the isolation and structure elucidation of the antibiotic carbazomycins from *Streptover-ticillium* species⁶. We reported the total syntheses of these unprecedented antibiotics starting from the iron-complexed cation **1** and the fully substituted arylamines **2** (Scheme 1)⁷. This work

Scheme 1

demonstrated that 3-oxygenated and 3,4-dioxygenated carbazoles are easily available in high overall yield by the iron-mediated construction of the carbazole framework.

A variety of 1-oxygenated carbazole alkaloids have been isolated by Chakraborty, Pezzuto, and Furukawa from higher plants of the genus *Murraya*⁸. Also these alkaloids could be synthesised by our method using the iron-complexed cation **1** and the arylamines **3** (Scheme 2)^{1,9}.

Scheme 2

Among the large number of carbazole alkaloids which have been isolated from *Murraya koenigii* by Chakraborty and coworkers are the 2-oxygenated derivatives shown in Scheme 3.

Scheme 3

Mukonidine¹⁰ and the corresponding aldehyde, mukonal¹¹, have been isolated from the stem bark of *Murraya koenigii*. 2-Methoxy-3-methylcarbazole (4)¹² was obtained from the seeds, and 2-hydroxy-3-methylcarbazole (5)¹³ from the roots of the same plant. It has been suggested that 3-methylcarbazole is the key intermediate in the biosynthesis of carbazole alkaloids in higher plants^{2a}. Chakraborty proposed that the C-3 methyl group of carbazoles is oxidised in vivo to functional groups (CH₂OH, CHO, COOH, COOCH₃)^{2b,c}. Thus, oxygenation of the 1-position and oxidation of the methyl group generates the alkaloids shown in Scheme 2⁸. Whereas oxygenation of the 2-position and eventual oxidation of the methyl group provides the 2-oxygenated

carbazoles presented in Scheme 3^{2b,c,10,11}. Moreover, 2-hydroxy-3-methylcarbazole is considered the crucial precursor for the biosynthesis of pyranocarbazole alkaloids¹⁴.

Because of the biosynthetic significance of the 2-oxygenated carbazole alkaloids described above we wanted to develop a versatile and convergent transition metal-mediated access to this class of compounds. In view of the success we had with the iron-mediated carbazole synthesis of 3-oxygenated, 3,4-dioxygenated, and 1-oxygenated carbazoles, we envisaged to apply the same methodology for 2-oxygenated carbazoles. In the present paper we report our preliminary studies directed towards a synthesis of 2-oxygenated carbazole alkaloids by consecutive iron-mediated C-C and C-N bond formation using the tricarbonyliron-complexed cation **1** and the arylamines **6** and **7**.

Results and Discussion

Literature precedence by our group has shown that a good yield for the oxidative cyclisation to mukonine which has a 3-methoxycarbonyl substituent on the carbazole skeleton was achieved^{1,9}. Hence we initially envisaged the synthesis of the structurally related mukonidine would be similar. Functional variation of the C-3 substituent, as performed for the 1-oxygenated carbazole alkaloids^{1,9}, should lead to mukonal as well. Therefore, methyl 4-aminosalicylate (**6**) was considered the common precursor of both natural products (cf. retrosynthetic analysis in Scheme 3).

The tricarbonyl[(1-5-η)-cyclohexadienyl]iron tetrafluoroborate (**1**) is provided on large scale almost quantitatively by complexation of 1,3-cyclohexadiene with pentacarbonyliron using a 1-aza-1,3-butadiene catalyst¹⁵ and subsequent hydride abstraction with triphenylcarbenium tetrafluoroborate¹⁶. Commercial 4-aminosalicylic acid (**8**) was quantitatively transformed to the methyl ester **6** using diazomethane. The C-C bond formation was achieved under the usual conditions by reaction of 2.2 equivalents of

the arylamine **6** with 1 equivalent of the iron-complexed cation **1** in acetonitrile at room temperature and provided the iron complex **9** in 86% yield (Scheme 4). The yield of the C–C bond formation was considerably higher than in the

Scheme 4

synthesis of mukonine¹. This outcome is explained by the hydroxy group in the 3-position of the arylamine which increases the nucleophilicity of the aromatic nucleus in the *ortho*-amino position. The reaction is completely regioselective and takes place exclusively in the less hindered *ortho*-amino position. This assignment is confirmed by the ¹H nmr spectrum of compound **9**, which exhibits two singlets of the aromatic protons at 6.10 and 7.57 ppm. The stereochemistry is supported by the doublet of triplet at 3.25 ppm of the tertiary proton. This downfield shift is caused by the effect of magnetic anisotropy of the iron atom and has been observed in related complexes described earlier^{1,7,17}.

Reaction of complex **9** with very active manganese dioxide¹⁸ did not afford the desired natural product via iron-mediated arylamine cyclisation. Even after 6 days in toluene at room temperature no significant turnover was detected. On the other hand, oxidation with iodine¹⁹ provided the

corresponding free ligand **10** in 15% yield. The structure assignment of the diene **10** is derived from the four signals of the four olefinic protons between 5.74 and 6.10 ppm in the ¹H nmr spectrum.

Earlier results in our laboratories indicated that oxidative cyclisations to carbazoles are not feasible with iron complexes having free hydroxy groups^{7,17}. Therefore, we decided to protect the hydroxy function by chemoselective *O*-acetylation of complex **9** to complex **11** (Scheme 5). Oxidation

Scheme 5

of complex **11** with very active manganese dioxide¹⁸ for 53 h at room temperature gave an inseparable mixture containing only traces of *O*-acetyl mukonidine as indicated by the ¹H nmr spectrum. Treatment of the iron complex **11** with iodine in pyridine¹⁹ afforded the free ligand **12** in 71% yield, demonstrating that this demetalation process is even much more efficient with the protecting group on the phenol. The structure of **12** is confirmed by the ¹H nmr spectrum which shows the four characteristic signals of the olefinic protons between 5.74 and 6.11 ppm. We had noted earlier¹⁷ that iodine in pyridine is more a reagent for demetala-

tion of tricarbonyl[η^4 -cyclohexadiene]iron complexes rather than for oxidative cyclisation as previously¹⁹ reported by others. Oxidation of complex **11** with thallium(III) trifluoroacetate under the standard conditions (CH_3OH , NaHCO_3 , 30 min, 0°) which have been successfully applied to the iron-mediated iminoquinone cyclisation²⁰ led only to decomposition of the starting material.

As a further alternative target for the synthesis of a mukonidine derivative we considered *O*-methylmukonidine, a known derivative of the natural product¹⁰. The required arylamine **13**²¹ was prepared in 70% yield by *O*-methylation of methyl 4-aminosalicylate (**6**). Electrophilic substitution of the arylamine **13** using the iron-complexed cation **1** in acetonitrile at room temperature afforded the iron complex **15** in 69% yield. The regiochemistry of complex **15** is confirmed by the two singlets at 6.13 and 7.70 ppm of the aromatic protons in the ¹H nmr spectrum and the stereochemistry is deduced from the doublet of triplet of the tertiary proton at 3.29 ppm. The results of the oxidations of the iron complex **15** were analogous to those obtained with the acetyl derivative **11**. Treatment of complex **15** with very active manganese dioxide¹⁸ led to an inseparable mixture of several compounds with one of them being the desired *O*-methylmukonidine¹⁰ as indicated by the ¹H nmr spectrum. On the other hand, oxidation of complex **15** with iodine in pyridine provided the free ligand **16** in 69% yield (Scheme 6). Again, the structure assignment of the diene **16** is based on its ¹H nmr spectrum which exhibits the four characteristic signals of the olefinic protons between 5.74 and 6.08 ppm. Although we found no appropriate method yet for oxidative cyclisation of the iron complexes **9**, **11** and **15**, we noted that iodine in pyridine represents an efficient reagent for the demetalation of these complexes. Therefore, this method of removing the tricarbonyliron unit constitutes a useful alternative for the standard procedure (reaction with trimethylamine *N*-oxide in acetone)²², which sometimes gives disappointing results in the case of arylamine-substituted cyclohexadienes.

Scheme 6

We then turned our attention to the synthesis of 2-methoxy-3-methylcarbazole (**4**) which according to our retrosynthetic analysis (Scheme 3) should derive from the commercially available 3-methoxy-4-methylaniline (**7**). Ether cleavage of **4** provides the biogenetically important 3-hydroxy-4-methylcarbazole (**5**)¹⁴, therefore, the arylamine **7** represents a potential precursor of both alkaloids. Moreover, oxidative cyclisation of the intermediate iron complex with concomitant oxidation of the C-3 methyl group to a formyl group, as reported in our total synthesis of murrayanine^{1,9}, would provide *O*-methylmukonal.

The electrophilic aromatic substitution of **7** with the iron-complexed cation **1** provided the iron complex **17** in 93% yield. Regio- as well as stereochemical assignment of this compound is based on its characteristic features in the ¹H nmr spectrum (two singlets at 6.14 and 6.82 ppm of the two aromatic protons and a doublet of triplet at 3.34 ppm of the tertiary proton). Treatment of **17** with very active manganese dioxide led only to slow decomposition of the starting material. However, reaction of complex **17** with iodine in pyridine afforded 2-methoxy-3-methylcarbazole (**4**; 11% yield) along

with the diene **18** 44% yield) (Scheme 7). This is the same ratio of carbazole and free ligand as previously obtained in the oxidation

of the *p*-toluidine substituted complex with the iodine/pyridine system¹⁷. The ¹H nmr spectrum of the diene **18** is similar to the dienes **10**, **12** and **16** described above. It shows two singlets of the two aromatic protons at 6.21 and 6.86 ppm and a signal of four olefinic protons between 5.65 and 6.30 ppm. The nmr spectral data of our synthetic carbazole **4** are in full agreement with those reported by Chakraborty *et al.* for the natural product^{12,14}.

Conclusion : The *C*-alkylated arylamines required for the synthesis of 2-oxygenated carbazole alkaloids are accessible in good to excellent yields. However, in contrast to systems previously studied by our group^{1,7,9}, the yield and selectivity of the oxidative cyclisation using very active manganese dioxide is not acceptable. In the presence of a methoxycarbonyl group in the 4-position of the arylamine moiety oxidation with iodine in pyridine leads exclusively to demetalation and affords the corresponding free ligands. While application of the same reagent provides the

2-methoxy-3-methylcarbazole (**4**) in 2 steps and 10% overall yield based on the iron-complexed cation **1**. We are currently searching for more selective methods of oxidative cyclisation as well as for alternative transition metal complexes in order to develop improved synthetic routes to 2-oxygenated carbazole alkaloids.

Experimental

All reactions were carried out by using dry and degassed solvents in an inert gas atmosphere (argon or nitrogen). Flash chromatography was performed using Baker silica gel (0.03–0.06 mm). Melting points were determined using Reichert hot stage. Ir spectra were recorded on Bruker IFS 25, Perkin-Elmer 580 and 1710 (FTIR), ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra on Bruker WP-80, WH-90, WP-200, AM-300 and AM-400 using tetramethylsilane or chloroform as internal standard and mass spectra on Finnigan MAT-312 having ionisation potential 70 eV.

Methyl 4-amino-2-hydroxybenzoate (6) : An ethereal solution of diazomethane (ca. 0.28 mmol/ml; 45 ml) was added over a period of 20 min to a solution of 4-amino-2-hydroxybenzoic acid (**8**; 1.53 g, 10.0 mmol) in diethyl ether (100 ml). The solution was stirred for further 20 min at room temperature and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure to afford methyl 4-amino-2-hydroxybenzoate (**6**; 1.67 g, 100%) as colourless crystals, m.p. 117–18°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 475, 3 381, 3 250, 2 951, 1 656, 1 641, 1 577, 1 516, 1 439, 1 356, 1 192, 1 154, 782 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (200 MHz; CDCl₃) 10.95 (1H, s), 7.61 (1H, d, *J* 9.2 Hz), 6.15 (2H, m), 4.10 (2H, br s), 3.87 (3H, s); MS (25°) *m/z* 167 (*M*⁺, 65), 137 (43), 136 (100), 108 (63), 100 (58); HRMS calcd. for C₈H₉NO₃ (*M*⁺) : 167.0582, found : 167.0583.

Tricarbonyl[1-4-η]-5-(2-amino-4-hydroxy-5-methoxycarbonylphenyl)-1,3-cyclohexadiene]iron (9) : A solution of the complex salt (**1**; 308 mg, 1.01 mmol) in acetonitrile (7 ml) was added to a solution of the arylamine (**6**; 369 mg, 2.21

mmol) in acetonitrile (5 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 25 h and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. Flash chromatography (ethyl acetate/light petroleum, 1 : 6) of the residue on silica gel provided the iron complex (**9**; 333 mg, 86%) as light yellow crystals, m.p. 163–66°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 497, 3 399, 2 953, 2 045, 1 967, 1 663, 1 631, 1 579, 1 500, 1 440, 1 357, 1 298, 1 264, 1 231, 1 205, 623, 564 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz; CDCl_3) 10.74 (1H, s), 7.57 (1H, s), 6.10 (1H, s), 5.55 (2H, m), 4.06 (2H, br s), 3.90 (3H, s), 3.25 (1H, dt, J 11.0, 3.5 Hz), 3.14 (2H, m), 2.35 (1H, ddd, J 15.0, 11.0, 3.9 Hz), 1.52 (1H, br d, J 15.0 Hz); ^{13}C nmr and DEPT δ (75 MHz; CDCl_3) 211.7 (CO), 170.3 (C=O), 161.7 (C), 150.7 (C), 128.5 (CH), 122.0 (C), 102.8 (C), 101.5 (CH), 85.7 (CH), 85.1 (CH), 63.8 (CH), 59.7 (CH), 51.8 (CH_3), 38.6 (CH), 30.9 (CH_2); MS (100°) m/z 385 (M^+ , 8), 357 (13), 329 (71), 301 (59), 299 (66), 269 (80), 267 (41), 241 (100), 239 (41), 212 (35), 210 (44); HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{FeNO}_6$ (M^+) : 385.0249, found : 385.0247.

2-(Cyclohexa-2,4-dienyl)-5-hydroxy-4-methoxycarbonylbenzeneamine (**10**) : Iodine (115 mg, 0.91 mmol) was added to a solution of the iron complex (**9**; 51 mg, 0.13 mmol) in pyridine (1 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h at room temperature and for further 2 h at 90°. The solution was cooled and sodium dithionite (23 mg) was added. The resulting mixture was stirred for 10 min at room temperature, then poured into 10% citric acid (10 ml) and extracted several times with diethyl ether. The combined organic layers were dried over magnesium sulphate. Evaporation of the solvent and flash chromatography (ethyl acetate/light petroleum, 1 : 9) of the residue on silica gel afforded the diene (**10**; 5 mg, 15%) as light brown crystals, m.p. 104–06°; ν_{\max} (CHCl_3) 3 500, 3 403, 2 928, 1 659, 1 628, 1 498, 1 439, 1 352, 1 281, 1 250, 1 095 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz; CDCl_3) 10.77 (1H, s), 7.56 (1H, s), 6.18 (1H, s), 6.10 (1H, m), 5.98 (1H,

m), 5.86 (1H, m), 5.74 (1H, m), 4.29 (2H, br s), 3.88 (3H, s), 3.58 (1H, m), 2.42 (2H, m); MS (50°) m/z 245 (M^+ , 100) 244 (84), 243 (26), 213 (32), 212 (77), 211 (31), 167 (45); HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_3$ (M^+) : 245.1052, found : 245.1052.

Tricarbonyl[1-4- η]-5-(4-acetoxy-2-amino-5-methoxycarbonylphenyl)-1,3-cyclohexadiene]iron (**11**) : A solution of the iron complex (**9**; 184 mg, 0.48 mmol) in tetrahydrofuran (6 ml) was added to a suspension of lithium hydride (8 mg, 1.0 mmol) in tetrahydrofuran (4 ml). The heterogeneous mixture was stirred at room temperature for 30 min and acetic anhydride (58 mg, 54 μl , 0.57 mmol) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for further 23 h, then poured into a saturated solution of ammonium chloride, and the aqueous layer was extracted several times with diethyl ether. The combined organic extracts were dried over magnesium sulphate. Removal of the solvent afforded crystals which were recrystallised from ethyl acetate/light petroleum. Flash chromatography (ethyl acetate/light petroleum, 1 : 3) of the mother-liquor on silica gel gave further product which was combined with the crystal fraction and provided the iron complex (**11**; 117 mg, 57%) as light yellow crystals, m.p. 205°d; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 387, 2 951, 2 045, 1 968, 1 751, 1 708, 1 630, 1 505, 1 441, 1 369, 1 297, 1 250, 1 176, 1 074, 623, 565 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz; $[\text{CD}_3]_2\text{SO}$) 7.62 (1H, s), 6.23 (1H, s), 5.96 (2H, br s), 5.74 (2H, m), 3.70 (3H, s), 3.40–3.20 (3H, m), 2.48 (1H, m), 2.21 (3H, s), 1.38 (1H, br d, J 15.2 Hz); ^{13}C nmr and DEPT δ (75 MHz; $[\text{CD}_3]_2\text{SO}$) 212.4 (CO), 169.3 (C=O), 164.5 (C=O), 151.8 (C), 150.4 (C), 129.6 (CH), 126.8 (C), 108.6 (C), 108.2 (CH), 86.7 (CH), 84.9 (CH), 65.6 (CH), 61.6 (CH), 51.4 (CH_3), 36.0 (CH), 32.0 (CH_2), 20.9 (CH_3); MS (190°) m/z 427 (M^+ , 6), 399 (12), 397 (5), 371 (41), 343 (100), 341 (11), 314 (96), 299 (93), 297 (20), 269 (51), 267 (36), 197 (74), 195 (49); HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{FeNO}_7$ (M^+) : 427.0354, found : 427.0356.

5-Acetoxy-2-(cyclohexa-2,4-dienyl)-4-methoxycarbonylbenzeneamine (12) : Iodine (94 mg, 0.74 mmol) was added to a solution of the iron complex (**11**; 46 mg, 0.11 mmol) in pyridine (1 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h at room temperature and for further 75 min at 90°. The solution was then cooled and sodium dithionite (19 mg) was added. The resulting mixture was stirred for 10 min at room temperature, then poured into 10% citric acid (10 ml), and extracted several times with diethyl ether. The combined organic layers were dried over magnesium sulphate. Removal of the solvent and flash chromatography (ethyl acetate/light petroleum, 1 : 3) of the residue on silica gel provided the diene (**12**; 22 mg, 71%) as colourless crystals, m.p. 90°; ν_{\max} (CHCl₃) 3 499, 3 398, 3 025, 2 953, 1 760, 1 709, 1 626, 1 280, 1 246, 1 230, 1 172, 736 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (200 MHz; CDCl₃) 7.80 (1H, s), 6.31 (1H, s), 6.11 (1H, m), 5.98 (1H, m), 5.87 (1H, m), 5.74 (1H, m), 4.32 (2H, br s), 3.81 (3H, s), 3.64 (1H, m), 2.41 (2H, m), 2.34 (3H, s); MS (230°) *m/z* 287 (*M*⁺, 39), 286 (27), 285 (10), 245 (41), 244 (76), 243 (43), 214 (37), 213 (59), 212 (100), 211 (86), 209 (53); HRMS calcd. for C₁₆H₁₇NO₄ (*M*⁺) : 287.1158, found : 287.1157.

Methyl 4-amino-2-methoxybenzoate (13) and methyl 4-(N-methylamino)-2-methoxybenzoate (14) : A solution of methyl 4-aminosalicylate (**6**; 167 mg, 1.0 mmol) in tetrahydrofuran (7 ml) was added to a suspension of lithium hydride (16 mg, 2.0 mmol) in tetrahydrofuran (2 ml) at room temperature. The mixture was stirred for 15 min at room temperature and dimethyl sulphate (189 mg, 142 μ l, 1.5 mmol) was added. The reaction mixture was heated at 65° for 1 h, subsequently cooled, poured into a saturated solution of ammonium chloride, and extracted with diethyl ether. The combined organic layers were dried over magnesium sulphate. Evaporation of the solvent and flash chromatography (diethyl ether) of the residue on silica gel provided the *N*-methylarylamine **14** as the less polar fraction and the arylamine **13** as the more polar fraction :

14 (21 mg, 11%), colourless crystals, ¹H nmr δ (90 MHz; CDCl₃) 7.80 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz), 6.16 (2H, m), 3.90 (3H, s), 3.86 (3H, s), 2.90 (3H, s); **13**²¹ (127 mg, 70%), colourless crystals, ¹H nmr δ (90 MHz; CDCl₃) 7.77 (1H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz), 6.27 (2H, m), 4.10 (2H, br s), 3.89 (3H, s), 3.86 (3H, s).

Tricarbonyl[1-4- η]-5-(2-amino-4-methoxy-5-methoxycarbonylphenyl)-1,3-cyclohexadiene]iron (15) : A solution of the iron complex salt (**1**; 226 mg, 0.74 mmol) in acetonitrile (8 ml) was added to a solution of the arylamine (**13**; 293 mg, 1.62 mmol) in acetonitrile (15 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 4 h at room temperature. Removal of the solvent under reduced pressure and flash chromatography (diethyl ether) of the residue on silica gel afforded the iron complex (**15**; 202 mg, 69%) as light yellow crystals, m.p. 140°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 373, 2 949, 2 045, 1 968, 1 703, 1 610, 1 567, 1 435, 1 295, 1 246, 1 220, 623, 564 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (200 MHz; CDCl₃) 7.70 (1H, s), 6.13 (1H, s), 5.55 (2H, m), 3.85 (3H, s), 3.81 (3H, s), 3.29 (1H, dt, *J* 11.1, 3.5 Hz), 3.15 (2H, m), 2.35 (1H, ddd, *J* 15.0, 11.1, 3.9 Hz), 1.55 (1H, br d, *J* 15.0 Hz); MS (160°) *m/z* 399 (*M*⁺, 4), 371 (5), 369 (5), 368 (8), 343 (93), 341 (11), 315 (100), 312 (64), 297 (39), 287 (58), 283 (41), 268 (36), 257 (58), 255 (49), 226 (72), 179 (91); HRMS calcd. for C₁₈H₁₇FeNO₆ (*M*⁺) : 399.0405, found : 399.0405.

2-(Cyclohexa-2,4-dienyl)-5-methoxy-4-methoxycarbonylbenzeneamine (16) : Iodine (70 mg, 0.55 mmol) was added to a solution of the iron complex (**15**; 63 mg, 0.16 mmol) in pyridine (1.5 ml) and the mixture was stirred for 1 h at 90°. The solution was then cooled and sodium dithionite (22 mg) was added. After stirring for 10 min at room temperature, the mixture was poured into 10% citric acid (13 ml), and extracted several times with diethyl ether. The combined organic layers were dried over magnesium sulphate. Removal of the solvent

and flash chromatography (diethyl ether) of the residue on silica gel afforded the diene (**16**; 28 mg, 69%) as light yellow crystals, m.p. 108–10°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 457, 3 368, 2 925, 1 681, 1 637, 1 614, 1 558, 1 439, 1 277, 1 244, 1 226, 1 089, cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (200 MHz; CDCl_3) 7.69 (1H, s), 6.21 (1H, s), 6.08 (1H, m), 5.97 (1H, m), 5.86 (1H, m), 5.74 (1H, m), 4.33 (2H, br s), 3.82 (6H, s), 3.61 (1H, m), 2.41 (2H, m); MS (110°) m/z 259 (M^+ , 100), 258 (92), 244 (6), 228 (24), 226 (26), 200 (17), 199 (16), 194 (40), 181 (27), 150 (22); HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_3$: (M^+) : 259.1208, found : 259.1207.

Tricarbonyl[(1-4- η)-5-(2-amino-4-methoxy-5-methylphenyl)-1,3-cyclohexadiene]iron (17) : A solution of the complex salt (**1**; 306 mg, 1.00 mmol) in acetonitrile (8 ml) was added to a solution of the arylamine (**7**; 300 mg, 2.19 mmol) in acetonitrile (4 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h at room temperature. Evaporation of the solvent under reduced pressure and flash chromatography (ethyl acetate/light petroleum, 1 : 6) of the residue on silica gel provided the iron complex (**17**; 329 mg, 93%) as light yellow crystals, m.p. 135°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 439, 3 355, 2 926, 2 042, 1 968, 1 948, 1 629, 1 511, 1 207, 626, 564, 491 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (400 MHz; CDCl_3) 6.82 (1H, s), 6.14 (1H, s), 5.51 (2H, m), 3.75 (3H, s), 3.50 (2H, br s), 3.34 (1H, dt J 11.1, 3.6 Hz), 3.18 (1H, m), 3.14 (1H, m), 2.35 (1H, ddd, J 15.1, 11.1, 4.0 Hz), 2.11 (3H, s), 1.59 (1H, br d, J 15.1 Hz); ^{13}C nmr and DEPT δ (100 MHz; CDCl_3) 212.1 (CO), 156.6 (C), 142.1 (C), 129.0 (CH), 122.0 (C), 116.7 (C), 99.1 (CH), 85.6 (CH), 84.9 (CH), 65.4 (CH), 60.3 (CH), 55.3 (CH_3), 38.3 (CH), 31.4 (CH_2), 15.5 (CH_3); MS (120°) m/z 355 (M^+ , 2), 327 (3), 300 (24), 272 (33), 270 (58), 214 (24), 213 (23), 193 (100), 137 (47); HRMS calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{FeNO}_4$ (M^+) : 355.0507, found : 355.0506.

2-Methoxy-3-methyl-9H-carbazole (4) and 2-(cyclohexa-2,4-dienyl)-5-methoxy-4-methylbenzene-

amine (18) : Iodine (160 mg, 1.26 mmol) was added to a solution of the iron complex (**17**; 128 mg, 0.36 mmol) in pyridine (3 ml) and the mixture was stirred for 1 h at 90°. The solution was cooled and sodium dithionite (50 mg) was added. After stirring for 10 min at room temperature, the mixture was poured into 10% citric acid (30 ml), and extracted several times with diethyl ether. The combined organic layers were dried over magnesium sulphate. Removal of the solvent and flash chromatography (ethyl acetate/light petroleum, 1 : 6) of the residue on silica gel afforded the carbazole **4** as the less polar fraction and the diene **18** as the more polar fraction : **4** (8 mg, 11%), colourless crystals, ^1H nmr δ (80 MHz; CDCl_3) 8.00–7.75 (2H, m), 7.78 (1H, br s), 7.45–7.05 (3H, m), 6.82 (1H, s), 3.89 (3H, s), 2.36 (3H, s); **18** (35 mg, 44%), yellow oil (partly crystallised), ^1H nmr δ (80 MHz; CDCl_3) 6.86 (1H, s), 6.21 (1H, s), 6.30–5.65 (4H, m), 3.74 (3H, s), 3.56 (3H, m), 2.40 (2H, m), 2.10 (3H, s).

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